

HOUSING TOPOLOGY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This “Housing Typology System” project was challenging to us when we decided to implement this project. We are sure that this project will be definitely helpful for the people to take the information about purchasing houses and properties according to their budget and requirement. We will try to implement this project in such way that this will be very easy to handle and operate. In this project we are using HTML, PHP and my SQL for developing our software. In this application we have created a home page on which new user can put his input and according to that system will provide all the required information regarding to the houses and related properties based on the user requirement.

KEYWORDS: Network traffic measurement, traffic analysis, HADOOP, ISP is Internet service provider.